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Research article

Precipitation and female experience are major determinants of the breeding performance of Canarian houbara bustards

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Precipitation is one of the main triggers of reproduction in desert-breeding birds. The unpredictability of rainfall patterns in arid environments has led species to adapt their breeding effort to episodes of abundant food after rainfall. The response is not the same for all individuals in a population, and may vary especially with the age and experience of each female. Here we investigate the effects of precipitation, temperature, body size and breeding experience, among other variables, on reproductive parameters of 20 females of Canarian houbara bustard (*Chlamydotis undulata fuertaventurae*), an endangered desert bird endemic of the eastern Canary Islands. Precipitation and breeding experience were the main determinants of female breeding performance. Higher rainfall determined an increase in nesting rate, and earlier autumn rains caused an advancement of nesting to October, allowing the breeding season to be extended to eight months. This favoured an extraordinary increase in productivity in more rainy breeding seasons, with 15 times more females nesting in the two most rainy winters than in dry years. In addition, females with more breeding experience showed a higher tendency to breed, higher nest attempt and fledging success, and longer breeding season, which allowed them to rear more chicks. A female even double brooded successfully in the same season, which, considering that chicks remain with the mother for up to six months, indicates a great capacity to optimise reproductive investment, by adapting to highly variable rainfall regimes. In recent decades, the eastern Canary Islands have undergone a process of aridification, and climate models predict a medium-term increase in the frequency and duration of drought periods. Thus, Canarian houbaras are particularly vulnerable to climate change, so measures are urgently needed to reduce their mortality and improve the quality of their habitat, in order to favour their reproduction and prevent their extinction.

Keywords: arid land, *Chlamydotis undulata fuertaventurae*, climate change, desert ecosystems, individual variation

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Introduction

The decision whether or not to breed in a given year and the timing of breeding are critical, as reproduction involves a considerable investment that affects not only breeding success, but may also risk own survival (Lack 1968, Daan et al. 1996, Dunn 2004). To maximize fitness in a changing environment, animals have evolved physiological and behavioural mechanisms to respond to environmental cues that allow them to make the right decisions at each stage of their life cycle (Wingfield 2008). Specifically for reproduction, in most birds breeding in temperate latitudes the main trigger for gonadal development and courtship is photoperiod, an entirely predictable external cue (Wingfield 1980, Hau et al. 1998, Dawson et al. 2001, Dawson 2008). Other less predictable cues such as temperature and food availability serve to modulate the exact timing of breeding within that photoperiod-defined physiological window (Wingfield et al. 1992, Deutsch et al. 2008, McNamara et al. 2011). This allows birds to match the period of maximum food demand of their offspring with maximum food availability, which indeed is the ultimate factor controlling the timing of breeding and the major determinant of breeding success (Lack 1950, 1968, Komdeur 1996, Both et al. 2006, Dawson 2008, McNamara et al. 2011). These processes and the underlying physiological mechanisms have been well studied in birds breeding in temperate regions of the northern hemisphere, where birds typically initiate breeding in response to the spring temperature increase (Visser et al. 2009, Schaper et al. 2012, Caro et al. 2013). However, in other latitudes where seasonal variations in photoperiod and temperature are less pronounced or follow different patterns birds may respond to other cues to initiate reproduction. For example, in tropical latitudes rainfall appears to be a fundamental trigger for breeding (Hau 2001, Şekercioglu et al. 2012, Chambers et al. 2013, Hidalgo Arazamendi et al. 2019).

The importance of rainfall as a trigger for reproduction has been also documented in birds breeding in desert areas (Immelmann 1970, Wiens 1991, Zann et al. 1995, Li and Brown 1999, Lloyd 1999, Morrison and Bolger 2002, Hau et al. 2004, Illera and Díaz 2006, Mares et al. 2017, Hidalgo-Arazamendi et al. 2019). Water is a limiting factor in many biological processes, including primary production (Rosenzweig 1968, Noy-Meir 1973, Seely and Louw 1980). In dryland ecosystems, the timing of grass greenup and senescence is much more dependent on precipitation than on temperature (Currier and Sala 2022). Herbaceous plants grow when it rains, favour the development of invertebrates, and these support birds during reproduction. Thus, the unpredictability of rainfall patterns in deserts makes reproduction of many species also episodic, i.e. dependent on occasional periods of resource abundance (Immelmann 1973, Evenari 1985, Shmida et al. 1986, Wiens 1991). The responses of species breeding in these ecosystems can be highly variable. Some of them simply do not breed in dry years (Boag and Grant 1984, Wiens 1991, Lloyd 1999, Tieleman 2002, Bolger et al. 2005, Illera and Díaz 2006). Others delay or

advance their reproductive cycle to coincide with periods of abundant rainfall, making them seasonal opportunistic breeders that do not rely on photoperiod or temperature (Brown and Li 1996, Leitner et al. 2003), and some are temperature but not rainfall-dependent breeders (Barrientos et al. 2007, Saint Jalme et al. 1996a, b, van Heezik et al. 2002).

Food availability in rainy years has been postulated as the ultimate cause not only of their timing of breeding, but also of their breeding performance (Rotenberry and Wiens 1991, Grant et al. 2000). In some species, higher productivity has been recorded not only when it rains shortly before laying, but also when it rains heavily during the preceding winter months (Li and Brown 1999, Morales et al. 2002), and even two years before (Koenig and Mumme 1988). Further studies are needed to know all details of the environmental cues governing the reproductive phenology of desert breeding species. Furthermore, it is not only important to understand the effects of temperature and precipitation on the timing of reproduction, but also on each of other parameters defining the breeding success, such as proportion of individuals breeding, clutch size, number of clutches and re-nesting probability, hatching and fledging success, and total number of offspring. Finally, not all individuals respond in the same way to environmental cues, female quality, experience and age being important factors in modulating these responses (Forslund and Pärt 1995, Verhulst and Nilsson 2008, Rebke et al. 2010).

In this study we analysed the effects of the two main environmental factors (precipitation, temperature) together with variables intrinsic to the individual (body size, breeding experience) on the main reproductive parameters in the Canary houbara bustard (*Chlamydotis undulata fuertaventurae*), a subspecies of African houbara bustard that inhabits semi-desert environments in the eastern Canary Islands. The aims of our study were to 1) quantify for the first time the main breeding parameters of this subspecies. In spite of being endangered, there are no published studies on the reproduction of Canary houbaras, with the exception of some productivity data in the context of a population survey (Alonso et al. 2020). 2) Investigate the influence of precipitation, temperature, female breeding experience and size, and date on the main breeding parameters: proportion of females nesting each year, nest initiation date, incubation success, fledging success, female re-clutching probability, productivity of juveniles per year, and length of the breeding season. According to previous studies with both houbara species, temperature seems to be the main factor associated with the onset of nesting, and abundant rainfall only contributes to extend the breeding season (Saint Jalme et al. 1996a, van Heezik et al. 2002, Maloney 2003, Hingrat et al. 2007, Azar et al. 2018), or to increase nest survival in older females (Bacon et al. 2017).

The Canary houbara is an endangered species, endemic to the eastern, most arid islands of the Canary archipelago, where rainfall is low and highly unpredictable, making it particularly sensitive to climate change (García et al. 2001, Bolger et al. 2005, Marcelino et al. 2020, Currier and Sala 2022). In fact, recent studies suggest that the species' decline

over the last decades on Fuerteventura island, where it was once most abundant but is now on the brink of extinction, may be partly due to the aridification of the habitat (Ucero et al. 2024a), a consequence of which would be that their current reproductive rate is not sufficient to compensate in the long term for natural mortality, urging for conservation to reduce mortality and improve habitat quality (Alonso et al. 2024a). It is therefore essential to know in detail how the reproductive performance of Canarian houbaras may be influenced by precipitation and temperature, which are the two main climatic factors that may continue to evolve unfavourably in the near future, leading the species to extinction within a few decades.

Methods

Study area and species

The study was carried out in Lanzarote, Fuerteventura and La Graciosa, the three easternmost islands of the Canary archipelago, which is located 140 km west of the northwestern coast of Africa. The subtropical-desert climate of these islands is tempered by the cold Canary Current and the northeasterly trade winds. The mean annual temperature is 21°C, and the average annual rainfall is 100–120 mm, concentrated in December–February, with lowest values in Fuerteventura, the most arid island of the archipelago. Summers are dry, with < 1 mm precipitation in June–August. The islands have a volcanic origin, and the vegetation is characterized by xerophytic shrubs, modified in some areas by goat grazing and farming activities.

The Canarian houbara is a subspecies of African houbara bustard endemic to the Canary Islands (Martín and Lorenzo 2001). It is classified as globally vulnerable following IUCN criteria (BirdLife International 2021), and as endangered in the Spanish Red List of Birds (Ucero et al. 2021). Canarian houbaras have their main stronghold in Lanzarote (440–452 birds), and smaller populations in Fuerteventura (85–109 birds) and La Graciosa (12–16 birds) (Alonso et al. 2020, Ucero et al. 2021). The species is polygynous (Collins 1984) and exhibits an exploded lek mating system (Hingrat and Saint Jalme 2005, Hingrat et al. 2007). It shows a moderate male-biased sexual size dimorphism (Alonso et al. 2023). The Canarian subspecies is a nocturnal, partial migrant (Abril-Colón et al. 2022a). One third of the individuals migrate in summer to non-breeding areas with a mosaic of shrubland and irrigated farmland where they forage on sweet potato fields, green fallows, alfalfas and orchards. Between late autumn and early spring, males concentrate at lek areas where they display at specific locations of their territories, to which they remain faithful over the breeding period and between years (Abril-Colón et al. 2022a). These sites are characterised by high visibility, low stone and vegetation cover, and far distance to human infrastructure (Ucero et al. 2024b). Females visit displaying males for mating and later take over all breeding duties (Gaucher 1995). Eggs are typically laid two or three

days apart, but hatching is relatively synchronized, suggesting that incubation starts once the clutch is completed (Gaucher 1995). Successfully breeding females normally raise one, less frequently two, and exceptionally three chicks that remain dependent of her for about 2–3 months (Saint Jalme and van Heezick 1996, Gelinaud et al. 1997, Combreau et al. 2002, Hingrat et al. 2007, Hardouin et al. 2012). During that time they do not initiate a new nest attempt, but if the first attempt fails or the chicks die, she may lay again. The nest is a shallow depression on the ground built by the female (Gaucher 1995). For each breeding attempt, the female chooses a different nest, generally in the vicinity of the previous one and within her territory, which she defends and to which she remains faithful year after year (Abril-Colón et al. 2022b). The chicks are precocial and follow her mother from their first day (Gaucher 1995). Adult houbaras are omnivorous, feeding mostly on herbaceous plants, while the diet of chicks is based on arthropods (Collins 1984, 1993, Saint Jalme and van Heezick 1996, Tigar and Osborne 2000). Canarian houbaras have no predators, except feral or free-ranging cats or dogs; Canarian ravens (*Corvus corax canariensis*), yellow-legged gulls (*Larus michahellis atlantis*), and common buzzard (*Buteo buteo insularum*) prey on eggs and chicks and may occasionally attack injured or debilitated adults (Ucero et al. 2021).

Data collection

We used data from 20 female houbara bustards captured in Lanzarote with nylon snares and equipped with backpack-mounted GSM/GPRS data loggers manufactured by e-obs GmbH, Gruenwald, Germany. The weight of the logger (25 g) plus harness was on average 2.15% of the female weight. All females were captured at foraging areas during the non-breeding season, in order not to put at risk their nesting process. Sex was established in the field using distinctive plumage features (Glutz et al. 1973, Gubin 1999), and confirmed by genetic analysis using DNA extracted from 1–2 contour feathers (Horreo et al. 2023).

The loggers recorded GPS locations at five-minute intervals continuously throughout 24 h from September 2020; before that date, GPS locations were recorded between 05:00 and 22:59 UTC, i.e. from 1 (summer solstice) to 3 hours (winter solstice) before sunrise to 1–3 hours after sunset. Loggers were provided with accelerometers (ACC) that registered the acceleration of the bird on a 3D space, providing a graphical representation of the bird's activities. We programmed the ACCs to register 15 seconds activity bouts every 15–60 minutes, depending on the phase of the study, between 05:00 and 21:00 UTC, with a byte count of 1188 and 16.7 Hz. Sequences of ACC graphs corresponding to each behaviour were obtained and matched to the different behaviours by comparing the different patterns on these graphs with field observations in which these behaviours were timed. To help determine to which behaviour corresponded each of the 15 second sequences, field observations were carried out on 10 marked individuals between

December 2018 and March 2019, for varying periods of time (720 hours in total) using a 20–60× telescope, from a distance of 1000 m and timing each behaviour of the observed individual. Comparison of these field observations with the ACC graphs allowed us to identify the ACC patterns reflected in the graphs that corresponded to the main activities of the birds. Data were downloaded via the telephone network, without having to recapture the birds, and stored in Movebank (<https://www.movebank.org/>). ACC data collected by the loggers were analysed using the Python-based AcceleRater application (Resheff et al. 2014; <http://accapp.move-ecol-minerva.huji.ac.il/>) to fit models and classify behaviour. A dataset consisting of 1722 samples and 10 behaviour types was used: display run (16.67%), vocalisation (7.95%), pre-copulatory movements (movements performed by males before copulation; 0.41%), walking (5.28%), feeding (30.31%), preening (6.97%), resting (1.45%), pre-display (1.68%), guarding (26.53%) and flight (2.73%). Five machine learning algorithms (5 models) were evaluated for use in classification of acceleration. For more details, see Abril-Colón et al. (2023).

Obtaining GPS locations every 5 minutes made it possible to know the exact position of each tagged female almost continuously throughout the 24 hours of the day. Combining GPS locations with data provided by the ACC we could determine when a female remained over several days in a fixed location, practically motionless, with only brief periods of movement for feeding, and interpreted that behaviour as incubation. This method enabled to fix the start and end dates of incubation (which coincide with the dates of respectively, laying of the last egg and hatching of the chicks; Saint Jalme and van Heezik 1996, Bacon 2013). We could also determine when incubation was not complete, although not the reason why the female stopped incubating. The use of this telemetry technique therefore allowed remote monitoring of the nesting phenology without causing any disturbance to the birds, as no visits to the nests were required. In fact, in order to avoid disturbing the females during incubation and the first weeks of chick rearing, we did not visit nests during these phases. However, this remote monitoring method did not allow us to infer the reasons why a nest might have been abandoned, such as predation, disturbances caused by goats, humans or other species, etc. We neither obtained information on clutch size and chick mortality.

The only visual controls of the families were carried out when the chicks were old enough to be unaffected. This was generally during May–June, coinciding with productivity sampling in the non-tagged population, when the chicks are, on average, about two months old (57.5 days, SD=21.74, n=10 chicks; Alonso et al. unpubl.). In 2023, two controls were necessary, respectively in January and June, to check the productivity of the two widely separated clutches laid that year. These controls of marked females allowed us to determine whether their chicks had survived the first weeks of life, when mortality is high. Therefore, they can be used as a reliable estimator of annual breeding success in the same way as

the annual productivity survey in the non-tagged population (Alonso et al. unpubl.).

It is worth noting that this productivity parameter, both in marked females and in the non-tagged population, does not include the final survival of the juveniles in their first year of life, as the productivity value is recorded when the offspring are still dependent on their mother and range in age from 2–3 weeks to about 3 months (unpubl.), so they may suffer additional first-year mortality, which some authors have estimated at approximately 10% (Combreau et al. 2003). However, in non-tagged populations productivity data can only be recorded when the young are still dependent on their mother and therefore recognisable as juveniles, which is not possible once they have reached the size of their mother or are already independent. Therefore, the time for recording productivity cannot be postponed beyond May–June. Juvenile independence can happen from the age of two months according to several authors (Saint Jalme and van Heezik 1996, Combreau et al. 2002, Hingrat pers. comm.). The same methodology for recording productivity is recommended for other steppe species (Alonso et al. 2005, Mañosa et al. 2022).

Productivity surveys

Productivity surveys were conducted in the non-tagged population in seven years in Lanzarote (seasons 2016–2017 to 2022–2023) and in four years in Fuerteventura (2019–2020 to 2022–2023). The surveys were carried out by car, covering most houbara areas of both islands between mid-May and late June, when most chicks have grown sufficiently for females with dependent chicks to show themselves, and have not yet reached adult size, so that they can be unambiguously identified as young of the year. We recorded all adult individuals (males and females) and young of the year, which could be differentiated by plumage characteristics (Glutz et al. 1973, Gubin 1999), and thanks to our experience acquired during capture and tagging. It was usual for houbara families to be isolated from other individuals, which helped to differentiate young from adults. Each survey involved two teams, each of two observers with one car, travelling along roads and tracks with binoculars, 20–60× spotting scopes and mobile phones with the Geotracker geolocation application. Sampling was carried out only on days with no rain or strong wind. The road network is sufficiently dense on both islands to allow vehicle access to virtually all areas potentially usable by houbara bustards, ensuring sufficient coverage. Surveys began at dawn and ended at dusk, with a four-hour break at midday (10:30–16:30 h UTC), when houbara bustards are most difficult to detect, as they rest immobile, standing or lying down, often hidden in the vegetation. The surveys were conducted at a speed of 15–20 km/h, with frequent stops (every 200–300 m) for close observation with binoculars or telescope on both sides without getting out of the vehicle. Longer stops (30–40 min) were also made at vantage points that allowed longer distance observation of the surroundings, with both observers getting out of the vehicle and using tripod-mounted telescopes to survey the terrain thoroughly in a wide radius

around them. Productivity is expressed as the number of young individuals per 100 non-juvenile females in the population. In addition to this percentage of juveniles, the average brood size (average number of chicks per female, = chicks / females with chicks) was calculated (Alonso et al. 2020 for more details on survey methods).

Breeding parameters

The following breeding parameters were analyzed: 1) Nesting rate (NR): the proportion of females that started incubating out of the total number of females tracked during a breeding season; 2a) Nest initiation date of first clutches (NIDF): first date of incubation of each female in each breeding season, considering 1 September of each breeding season as day 1; (2b) Nest initiation date, average of all clutches (NIDA): first date of incubation of all clutches, including first and replacement clutches (following the approach of Azar et al. 2018, 2022); the aim of 2a was to describe the variables determining the absolute onset of laying in each year, whereas 2b aims to describe the variables determining the onset of laying throughout the breeding season (see predictors in each case below, in Statistical analyses); the approach used for NIDA (Azar et al. 2018, 2022) was also used in a model with only first clutches (NIDF2); 3) Incubation success (IS): the proportion of clutches that survived over the whole incubation period; 4) Nesting attempt success (NAS): whether or not a clutch (including incompletely and fully incubated clutches) successfully produced live chicks by the age of 2 months; 5) Fledging success (FS): whether or not a clutch that was successfully incubated (i.e. over 23 days) produced live chicks by the age of 2 months; 6) Female re-clutching probability (FRCP): probability of a female laying a replacement clutch after an unsuccessful first nesting attempt (either in the egg or chick phase); 7) Productivity (P): number of offspring fledged per female per year; 8) Length of the breeding season (LBS): for each female in each study year, days between the start of incubation and the last date the female was seen with a dependent chick (in the case of successfully breeding females), or the last incubation date (in cases of failed breeding attempts, due to clutch loss or early death of chicks); non-breeding females were assigned a zero.

Statistical analysis

The influence of predictor variables on breeding parameters was modeled by means of generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) using package 'lme4' (Bates et al. 2015) in R ver. 2.15.1 (www.r-project.org). We used binomial errors and logit link function for all parameters with a binomial response variable (NR, NIDA, NIDF, IS, NAS, FS and FRCP), and Poisson distribution for P and LBS (McCullagh and Nelder 1989). Untransformed variables were used for GLMM analyses, as normality is not required (Guisan and Zimmermann 2000).

Female and year were included as random factors in all models to account for repeated measures, except for NIDA

and NIDF2, where year was the only random factor. In all models we included as predictor variables the accumulated precipitation and the mean temperature, measured either over one or two months before the start of incubation (monthly or bi-monthly temperature and rainfall values during the pre-laying period, following van Heezik et al. 2002), or during the nesting and breeding process, depending on the reproductive parameter analysed. Precipitation and temperature were averaged from values recorded at eight meteorological stations distributed over the houbara range in Lanzarote. The island is small and, although some rains were quite localised, the dates with significant rainfall were generally the same at all stations, so averaged precipitation values adequately represented the precipitation at the nests analysed. Other predictors used in most models were female size and female breeding experience, estimated as the percentage of years she nested out of the total number of years she was monitored. Female size was the score of the first component of a Principal Component Analysis of log-transformed morphometrical measurements (wing chord, wing arch, tail length, tarsus length, central toe length, head length, bill length; Supporting information). We performed PCAs both including and excluding weight, and obtained in both cases similar factor structure and variance explained. In the first case, weight showed a loading of 0.74 in PC1, which also included high loadings for all measurements of all bony structures (tarsus, central toe, head and bill). This was the factor best defining the overall size of the female, while factor 2 included high loadings for measurements of feather structures (both measures of wing), and tail did not show high loadings on either of these two PCA factors (Supporting information). In line with this result, PC1 of the PCA excluding weight was positively correlated with weight ($r=0.67$). As an index of female size we finally used PC1 excluding weight, since measurements of bone structures are better indicators of the size of the female than weight, which is subjected to seasonal variations and also varies with body condition (Saint Jalme et al. 1996a, b, Jacquet 1998, Alonso et al. 2023). To model Productivity (P), we also included Female breeding effort, estimated as the number of clutches a female laid in a given breeding season. Finally, in some models we also included date as a measure of time (Azar et al. 2018, 2022), Laying date (the first day of incubation of a clutch), Clutch order (first, or replacement – second, third – clutches), and Duration of incubation in days (Supporting information, for details of response variables, units of analysis, sample sizes, and predictors used in each model). We used Akaike's information criterion corrected for small sample sizes (QAIC_c) to rank GLMM models, and Akaike weights (w) to assess model likelihood and uncertainty (Burnham and Anderson 2004). When the analysis of a reproductive parameter resulted in more than one plausible model ($\Delta AIC \leq 2$), we performed model averaging to identify the most relevant predictor variables.

Additional analyses included Spearman rank correlations between annual values of the following breeding parameters, measured on the sample of 20 tagged females: date when first clutch started versus date when first significant rainfall

(> 5mm) occurred, weighted average date when first clutches started in all females versus weighted average date of first rainfalls, total precipitation versus nesting rate each year, total precipitation versus duration of the breeding season, mean temperature versus nesting rate each year, weighted average date when first clutches started versus mean temperature over the first two months of each breeding season, mean temperature over the breeding season versus duration of the breeding season. A precipitation period was considered to have ended when the number of days without rainfall between two rainfall dates exceeded the number of days since the first rainfall.

Results

Annual variation in breeding parameters

On average, 60.5% of the females nested each year, 73.1% of which completed incubation (Table 1). Only 28.7% of these managed to rear chicks to fledging, which represents 13.2% of all tagged females, i.e. one out of 7.6 females in the population (Table 1). These figures correspond to an average annual productivity of 14.7 chicks raised to fledging per 100 females in the population (Table 1). Only one of the nine females that reared chicks up to fledging succeeded in doing so in two years of the study period (2018–2019 and 2022–2023). In this second year, that female managed to raise two chicks in two consecutive nestings, being the only one that was able to raise chicks up to fledging in two nestings in the same year. From the start of her first clutch on 5 November to the date of our last control when the chick of the second clutch was

77 days old, the female had devoted 222 days (61% of the year) to breeding.

Factors influencing breeding parameters

Among all predictor variables analysed, precipitation and female experience showed the strongest effects on most reproductive parameters studied (Table 2; see also Supporting information). Higher rainfall, both preceding clutch initiation and throughout the laying period, and greater female experience, had a clear positive effect on nesting rate (Table 2). Temperature preceding clutch initiation also showed a positive effect on nesting rate, although it was probably simply due to higher values occurring in the Canary Islands during the pre-laying period (October–November). In fact, the temperature coefficient turned to be negative when considering the whole breeding period in winter (1 September–13 March; Table 2). Because of this, and since interannual variations in temperature for a given date are very low in our study area, temperature has little potential to explain variations in nesting rate, as well as in other reproductive parameters. Therefore, we repeated this model and also final models of other breeding parameters excluding temperature. The significant predictors retained in the model for nesting rate excluding temperature were female experience and precipitation in the two months preceding incubation.

Precipitation in the two months preceding incubation showed a significant or marginally significant positive effect on all nest initiation date models (Table 2). An effect of temperature was also observed in NIDF, but not in NIDA and NIDF2. Nest attempt success and fledging success models

Table 1. Annual values of the breeding parameters of the 20 tagged female houbara bustards over the 5 years of study. Mean values and standard deviations (SD) for the whole study period are also shown.

	2018–2019	2019–2020	2020–2021	2021–2022	2022–2023	Mean values	SD
Sample of tagged females ¹	12	18	17	15	13	15.0	2.5
Number of females nesting	6	1	14	12	10	8.8	5.3
Nesting rate (% of females nesting out of those tagged)	50.0	5.6	82.3	80.0	84.6	60.5	32.8
Number of females completing incubation	5	1	12	5	6–7	5.8	3.9
% of tagged females completing incubation	41.7	5.6	70.6	33.3	46.2	39.5	23.5
Incubation success (% of laying females completing incubation)	83.3	100	85.7	41.7	54.5	73.1	24.1
Number of females that raised chicks to fledging	2	0	2	1	4	1.8	1.5
% of tagged females that raised chicks to fledging	16.7	0.0	11.8	6.7	30.8	13.2	11.6
% of successfully incubating females that raised chicks to fledging	40.0	0.0	16.67	20.0	66.7	28.7	25.6
Total number of chicks raised to fledging	2	0	2	1	5	2.0	1.9
Mean number of chicks raised to fledging per successful female	1.00	-	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.06	0.1
Annual productivity (= total chicks raised to fledging × 100/ tagged females)	16.7	0.0	11.8	6.7	38.5	14.7	14.6

¹ Because the 20 females were captured and tagged between May 2018 and May 2019, and due to the mortality of 10 females over the five years of study (autumn 2018 to autumn 2023), the sample of females on which reproductive parameters were calculated varied between years, from 12 individuals in 2018–2019 to 18 in 2019–2020.

Table 2. Coefficients and statistical significance of predictor variables selected in the best models ($\Delta AIC \leq 2$) for each breeding parameter analysed in female Canary houbars bustards (see the Supporting information for details of the model parameters, and for a list of all plausible models before model averaging). For breeding parameters with more than one plausible model, the values after performing model averaging are given. A dash indicates that the covariate was not included in the starting model; NS indicates that the covariate was not retained in the model. Significance codes: *** = $p < 0.001$, ** = $p < 0.01$, * = $p < 0.05$, () = $p < 0.1$, no asterisk = not significant.

Breeding parameters ¹	Predictor variables ²										
	Precipitation 2 months before clutch initiation ²	Precipitation during the breeding period ³	Temperature 2 months before clutch initiation ²	Temperature during the breeding period ³	Female size	Female breeding experience	Female breeding effort	Ordinal date	Laying date	Clutch order	Duration of incubation
Nesting rate	0.202**	-	2.525*	-	-0.092	22.431**	-	-	-	-	-
Nesting rate (excluding temperature)	0.155*	-	-	-	0.026	17.761**	-	-	-	-	-
Nesting rate ³	-	0.064***	-	-8.728*	-0.023	12.396***	-	-	-	-	-
Nest initiation date (NIDF, Supporting information)	-0.002**	-	-0.169***	-	NS	NS	-	-	-	-	-
Nest initiation date (excl. temperature)	-0.003(*)	-	-	-	-0.051	0.253	-	-	-	-	-
Nest initiation date (NIDA, Supporting information)	0.012(*)	-	-0.114	-	-	-	-	0.005(*)	-	-	-
Nest initiation date (NIDF2, Supporting information)	0.012(*)	-	-0.167	-	-	-	-	0.004	-	-	-
Incubation success	-	0.048	-	0.395	0.290	-	-	-0.012	0.873	-	-
Incubation success (excl. temperature)	-	NS	-	-	0.310	NS	-	-0.014	0.974	-	-
Nest attempt success	-	0.503	-	NS	-0.583	141.56***	-	-0.594	32.706	-	-
Fledging success	-	0.016	-	-	-8.872	115.73**	-	-0.595	-0.689	-	-
Female re-clutching probability	-	0.019	-	-	NS	-	-	-0.019*	-1.620*	-	-0.148**
Productivity	-	0.030**	-	-	NS	3.796	NS	-	-	-	-
Productivity (precipitation measured from 1 month before start of first clutch to start of last clutch)	-	0.024**	-	-	NS	3.808	NS	-	-	-	-
Productivity (precipitation measured between 1 September and 13 March)	-	0.018(*)	-	-	0.310	3.509	0.086	-	-	-	-
Length of the breeding season	-	0.060***	-	-0.551	0.017	8.819***	-	-	-	-	-
Length of the breeding season (excluding temperature)	-	0.053***	-	-	NS	8.839***	-	-	-	-	-
Length of the breeding season ³	-	0.031***	-	0.316	0.013	8.899***	-	-	-	-	-
Length of the breeding season (excluding temperature)	-	0.032***	-	-	NS	8.897***	-	-	-	-	-

¹ See definitions of breeding parameters and predictor variables in Methods; ² the results were very similar using rainfall and temperature measured within one month before the onset of laying; here we present the 2-month results because the difference between the first significant rainfall and the first laying was 52.6 days, i.e. nearly 2 months; ³ accumulated precipitation and mean temperature were measured over different periods of the breeding process, depending on the breeding parameter analysed (see the Supporting information for details).

showed a strong positive effect of female breeding experience (Table 2). The probability of females laying a replacement clutch decreased with the progress of the breeding season (date), clutch order, and duration of incubation of the first clutch (Table 2).

Finally, all productivity models showed a positive effect of precipitation (Table 2). Breeding experience was retained in all models with near significant coefficients ($p=0.069$ – 0.136), but only in one did it reach marginal significance before model averaging (Supporting information; in model 'Productivity with precipitation measured over a reduced breeding period', third candidate model 'Productivity with precipitation measured between 1 September and 13 March', where breeding experience had a $p=0.069$). All models for length of the breeding season showed strong positive effects of precipitation and female breeding experience (Table 2).

Effect of precipitation and temperature on the start and duration of the breeding season

Over the five years of study, the date when the earliest nesting female started incubation was positively correlated with the date of first significant rainfall ($r_s=0.97$, $p=0.005$; Fig. 1a). Positive correlations were also found between weighted average dates of first precipitation and onset of first clutches ($r_s=1.00$, $p=0.017$; Fig. 1b), and between the average duration of the breeding season for all nesting females and the total rainfall recorded in each season ($r_s=1.00$, $p=0.017$; Fig. 1c). We found no equivalent relationships with temperature, i.e. mean autumn temperatures (1 September–1 December) were not correlated with the dates when incubation started ($r_s=-0.80$, $p=0.13$), and mean temperatures over the whole breeding season (1 September–30 April) were not correlated with the duration of the breeding season ($r_s=0.10$, $p=0.95$).

The delay in nesting with respect to first rains was calculated from values in Fig. 1. Females started laying on average 61.9 days after the weighted average date when first rainfalls occurred (SD=11.7, minimum=47 days in 2022–2023, maximum=79 days in 2019–2020) (Fig. 1b). As for the earliest clutch in each year, it was laid on average 52.6 days after the first rainfall (SD=19.0, minimum=28 days in 2022–2023, maximum=70 days in 2019–2020) (Fig. 1a).

Overall nesting rate, duration of incubation and replacement clutches

Of the 20 tagged females, 16 (80%) nested in at least one of the study years. Thirteen of them (81%) laid replacement clutches when the first clutch was lost. In total, 71 clutches were recorded over the five years of study, of which only 40 (56.3%) were incubated over the whole 23-day incubation period. Forty-six were first clutches and the rest were replacement clutches, so each of the 16 nesting females laid on average 1.54 clutches per season (0.92 clutches per female if including the four females that never nested and years in which regularly nesting females did not nest).

The duration of incubation was 23.1 days (SD=1.4, range 20–26; i.e. similar to values reported for the African subspecies and MacQueen's bustard: 23 days, Gaucher 1995, Hardouin et al. 2012; 22.6 days, Maloney 2003), and that of failed incubations was 10.7 days (SD=4.6, range 3–17). Incubation success was highest in second clutches (76.9%), but the fledging success of fully incubated first clutches was double that of second clutches, and third clutches had no success (33%, 18%, and 0%, respectively).

Breeding phenology

The nesting period alone extended over more than six months, between 22 October, the first incubation start date (2022–2023 season), and 9 May, the date of termination of the last incubation (2021–2022 season) (Supporting information). In two of the study years, females laid only one clutch; in two other years some females laid a replacement clutch when their first clutch failed, and in one year (2020–2021) nine females laid a replacement clutch and three of them laid three clutches (Supporting information). The maximum length of the nesting period occurred in 2022–2023, with one female completing incubation of her second clutch 145 days after initiating her first clutch on 5 November 2022.

Individual variation in breeding success

Females that nested earlier in the season had higher breeding success, whether expressed as mean number of chicks reared per year ($r=-0.56$, $n=16$ females, $p=0.025$), or as mean number of chicks reared per nesting ($r=-0.57$, $n=16$ females, $p=0.020$). However, there was no significant relationship between nest initiation date and female weight, size, or reproductive experience ($r=-0.34$, $n=16$, $p=0.194$; $r=-0.39$, $n=16$, $p=0.135$; $r=0.07$, $n=20$, $p>0.10$, respectively), nor between female weight or size and mean juvenile productivity ($r=0.09$, $n=16$, and $r=0.04$, $n=16$, $p>0.10$ in both cases, respectively). The average annual productivity of a female was positively correlated with her breeding experience ($r=0.378$, $n=20$, $p=0.05$). Details of female productivity and comparison with values obtained in the non-tagged population are given in the Supporting information.

Discussion

The results of this study show that precipitation is the most important environmental factor determining the breeding performance of Canarian houbara bustards. The timing and amount of rainfall affected the timing of breeding, nesting rate, length of the breeding season, and productivity. In years with early autumn rainfall, females started nesting earlier, allowing for a longer breeding season, which favored a higher productivity. In addition, in more rainy years females nested in higher proportions, and their breeding season was longer,

Figure 1. Correlations between (a) dates of first significant precipitation (> 5 mm over at least 2 consecutive days) and date when the first female started incubation, (b) weighted average dates when first precipitation occurred and incubation of first clutches started (weighted values were obtained considering both the amount of precipitation and the date when each rain occurred during the laying period of first clutches, together with the numbers of first clutches occurring on each date), and (c) total precipitation over the breeding period (September–March) and mean duration of the breeding season (days between the start of incubation and the last date the female was seen with a dependent chick, in the case of successfully breeding females; or the last incubation date, in cases of failed breeding attempts due to clutch loss or early death of chicks. Vertical bars = SD, numbers of females are given next to each breeding season). Dates are expressed as ordinal dates, starting on 1 September of each breeding season.

also favoring a higher productivity. Female breeding experience also had a clear positive effect on breeding success, with experienced females showing a greater tendency to breed, higher nest attempt success and fledging success, and longer breeding seasons.

In this study, we investigated for the first time the breeding phenology and performance of the Canary houbara. The use of GSM/GPRS loggers equipped with accelerometers allowed us to collect GPS locations almost continuously, enabling us to accurately determine the beginning and end of incubation without having to make periodic visits to nesting females that would have disturbed them. Negative effects of periodic breeding controls have been reported for houbaras (Combreau et al. 2002) among other bird species (Bergan and Smith 1993, Cox and Afton 1998, Miller et al. 1998), especially in years with high predator density. Combreau et al. (2002) suggested that tagging nestlings may decrease their survival, and recommended tracking females as a less detrimental method.

Influence of precipitation on the timing of breeding

Female houbaras initiated incubation on average two months after the first autumn rains. A previous study in Fuerteventura found a correlation between arthropod availability and rainfall one month earlier (Illera and Díaz 2006), so two months was sufficient time for the development of herbaceous vegetation and associated arthropod communities that constitute the bulk of the offspring diet. Thus, the time of maximum food demand for broods coincides with the time of maximum availability, consistent with the hypothesis that this coincidence is the ultimate factor controlling the timing of breeding in birds (Lack 1950, 1968, Komdeur 1996, Both et al. 2006, Dawson 2008, McNamara et al. 2011).

The difference between the earliest and latest breeding onset was six months, a period that allows Canary houbaras to qualify as seasonal opportunistic breeders, like other species of these islands or others in similar latitudes with long physiological windows during which reproduction can be initiated (Leitner et al. 2003, Illera and Díaz 2006). Adding the chick rearing time up to independence, the period that Canary houbaras devote to breeding is even longer, reaching up to seven and eight months in two females, both in the 2022–2023 season.

Particularly striking is the ability of Canary houbaras to advance nesting to early autumn, when the days are still shortening, which discards the increase in photoperiod as a triggering factor to start breeding in this species. The lengthening of the breeding season in rainy years has been reported for other species of arid ecosystems, and usually occurs by advancing breeding when autumn rains start earlier (Zann et al. 1995, Leitner et al. 2003). Our results suggest that in Canary houbaras the total duration of nesting depends more on the advancement of the first clutch than on the number of clutches or an extension of the nesting period in late spring. In case of early autumn rains, houbaras may nest as early as October, and if sufficient rains continue,

nesting will last until spring. The end of the breeding season is probably determined by the end of rains and lack of food, and by migration or molting, which are incompatible with reproduction (Farner 1964, Farner and Wingfield 1980, Zuberogoitia et al. 2018; but see Serventy 1971). In some species the gonads remain active during a large part of the year (Perfito et al. 2007, Hahn et al. 2008, Tökölyi et al. 2011), although in houbaras gonadal activity and molting seem to be mutually excluding (Saint Jalme et al. 1996a).

The ability of Canary houbaras to advance nesting in rainy autumns allows them to breed twice successfully in the same breeding season. Successful double brooding in the same season has also been reported in the nominal subspecies (van Heezik et al. 2002, Hingrat et al. 2007) and in MacQueen's bustards (Maloney 2003), although the latter study did not confirm fledging of the chicks of the second clutch.

Temperature seemed to have no effect as a reproductive trigger in Canary houbaras. Illera and Díaz (2006) also found no influence of temperature on laying date, length of the reproductive season, reproductive effort, or reproductive success of the Canary stonechat. The low interannual and monthly variation in temperature in the Canary Islands, and the fact that temperatures are higher in autumn when houbaras start nesting and lower in winter during the main nesting period, are probably the reasons why this variable has little potential as a trigger for breeding in Canary houbaras. These results contrast with those of houbaras breeding in more continental climates in Africa and Asia. Studies with captive or reintroduced individuals of the nominate subspecies and MacQueen's bustard did not find a clear relationship between rainfall and the onset of laying. In some studies, a correlation was observed with temperature but not with precipitation (Saint Jalme et al. 1996a, van Heezik et al. 2002, Maloney 2003). Van Heezik et al. (2002) found that females nested earlier and in greater proportions after a cool winter. However, Gelinaud et al. (1997) suggested that spring rainfall would trigger houbara breeding in Saudi Arabia; and Bacon et al. (2017) observed that, in African houbara only, hatching success increased in years with more winter rainfall. Finally, in a free-ranging population Azar et al. (2018) concluded that rainfall had no effect on breeding onset date, but did have an effect on duration.

Effect of precipitation and female experience on breeding performance

Our models confirm that rainfall was not only the main factor triggering the timing of breeding in Canary houbaras, but also a major factor contributing to increasing other important parameters: nesting rate, length of the breeding season, and productivity. In the year with the heaviest autumn rains (2022–2023) the nesting rate was 15 times higher than in the least rainy year (2019–2020). Nesting rate is very important for the overall productivity of the population, as it determines how many females will breed in a season. As for the

length of the breeding season, models confirm not only the effect of early autumn rain as a trigger, but also that of winter rains in prolonging the breeding season. Both parameters, nesting rate and length of the breeding season, also appear to be significantly influenced by female breeding experience, via two mechanisms. First, by increasing the nesting rate, i.e. more experienced females are more likely to nest; and second, by extending the breeding season. The models also show positive effects of experience on nest attempt success and fledging success.

Although models did not confirm a significant influence of female experience on productivity, its influence is clear from the analysis of average reproductive parameters of the female. This analysis showed that early nesting females had higher productivity. In addition, although the correlations between each female's nesting date, her size, reproductive experience, and reproductive success do not allow a very clear conclusion on the ultimate cause of the greater success of earlier nesting females, it does seem clear that more experienced females achieve higher productivity values. Models also confirmed that experience is more important than age in determining productivity. More experienced females are more likely to nest, extend their breeding season mainly by nesting earlier, have better nest attempt and fledging success values, and thus manage to rear more chicks.

Overall, our results for incubation success and fledging success in first, second, and third clutches, together with those of the models and the correlations of mean values for each female, suggest that if rainfall occurs, the optimal strategy is to nest as early as possible, allowing extension of the breeding effort over more months and thus achieving higher productivity. In the African houbara and MacQueen's bustard, later nesting has also been shown to be less successful, with smaller clutch size and lower egg volume (Bacon 2013, Azar et al. 2018, Monnier-Corbel et al. 2022). This strategy of nesting as soon as possible is normally followed in many species by older and more experienced females (Forslund and Pärt 1995, Gruebler and Naef-Daenzer 2010), including African and Asian houbara bustards (van Heezik et al. 2002, Bacon 2013, Bacon et al. 2017, Azar et al. 2022), and is probably also followed by female Canary houbars. In African houbars, it has been shown that for any age cohort, the reproductive success of earlier-breeding females is higher (Bacon et al. 2017), and that age has a positive effect on nesting probability, egg volume, re-clutching probability, and advancement of egg-laying date (Azar et al. 2022). Maloney (2003) also observed that older females achieved higher incubation success than two-year-old females, and that one-year-old females were unsuccessful. The decline in reproductive success as the season progresses may be due to a progressive deterioration of environmental conditions (Gruebler and Naef-Daenzer 2010). In both North Africa and the Canary Islands, higher temperatures and lower rainfall as spring progresses must lead to a decrease in food resources on which chick growth depends, which would have favored this adaptation to breeding as early as possible (Hingrat et al. 2007, Bourass et al. 2012, Abril-Colón et al. 2022b).

The high frequency of replacement clutches in the Canary houbara is consistent with similar observations in other houbars. Female African houbars and MacQueen's bustards can lay up to two broods (Saint Jalme et al. 1996a, Combreau and Launay 1999, Combreau et al. 2002, van Heezik et al. 2002, Hingrat et al. 2007, Bacon 2013, Sorci et al. 2023).

Conclusions and prospects in a climate change scenario

In sum, the wide variability in the breeding timing and performance of the Canary houbara demonstrates its ability to adapt to highly variable rainfall regimes typical of desert environments, and to optimise its reproductive investment by taking advantage of periods of maximum food availability after the rains. This strong dependence of its breeding performance on rainfall raises the question of what influence periods of several years of drought and the progressive desertification of the eastern islands of the archipelago may have in the mid-term species demographics. It is true that high productivity and the possibility of double nesting in rainy years is likely a crucial mechanism that may have helped to maintain the population to date, by allowing negative demographic trends from drier years to be recovered. For example, productivity in Fuerteventura in 2022–2023 was the highest observed in both islands in the last seven years, surpassing even those of Lanzarote where in normal years it is usually higher than in Fuerteventura, and years like this from time to time can alleviate declining trends on this island (Ucero et al. 2021, 2024a). However, over the last decades there has been a process of land aridification in Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, and La Graciosa (Martin et al. unpubl., 2015, Máyer and Marzol 2016), and in the short and medium term an increase in the duration and intensity of droughts in the Canary Islands is predicted (De Castro et al. 2005, Carrillo et al. 2023, IPCC 2023). Furthermore, the significant relationship between rainfall and the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) observed in the five western islands of the archipelago does not occur in Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, and La Graciosa, where rainfall regimes are much more unpredictable and of much lower magnitude, with rainfall occurring only on 31% of the days when there is rain in the western islands (García et al. 2001). Arid ecosystems are known to be particularly vulnerable to climate change, in part due to the low and unpredictable precipitation regimes (Noy-Meir 1973, Bolger et al. 2005).

These processes of drought and aridification of the terrain have probably been determinant in the marked houbara population decline in Fuerteventura in recent times (Ucero et al. 2024a), and could accelerate this decline in the future throughout its entire distribution area. To mitigate these effects, measures to prevent anthropogenic mortality and improve habitat quality are urgently needed (Ucero et al. 2021, Alonso et al. 2024a). Among these, it is necessary to ensure the conservation and restoration of natural shrublands (especially *Launaea* shrublands) where houbara bustards breed, and to maintain an appropriate mixture of shrubland,

green fallows, and a few irrigated fields in some areas of the islands as the best habitat during the driest months of the year, when food resources at many breeding areas are scarcer (Abril-Colón et al. 2022a, b). These measures are especially important and urgent on the island of Fuerteventura, where Canary houbaras are on the brink of extinction.

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Author contributions

Juan C. Alonso: Conceptualization (lead); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (lead); Resources (equal); Supervision (lead); Writing - original draft (lead); Writing - review and editing (lead). **Inmaculada Abril-Colón:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Writing - review and editing (equal). **Alberto Ucero:** Data curation (supporting); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Writing - review and editing (equal). **Carlos Palacín:** Data curation (supporting); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Writing - review and editing (equal).

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the authors but restrictions apply to the availability of these data, which were used under license from the Government of the Canary Islands for the current study, and so are not publicly available until the contract 2021020055 has been finalised and all results are published. Data will be available from the authors when the current studies are finished, upon reasonable request and with permission of the Government of the Canary Islands.

Data are available from the Dryad Digital Repository: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.tht76hf7> (Alonso et al. 2024b).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

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